

MAKING A TINCTURE FROM WILD WATERMELON ROOT AND ITS USE FOR STROKES

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Actuality: Cardiovascular diseases, particularly stroke, are widespread among the population, independently of age. Therefore, a pressing task is the in-depth scientific study and development of homeopathic remedies with a pronounced pharmacological effect and low toxicity from plants growing in Kyrgyzstan and used in folk medicine. One such promising remedy is a tincture of wild watermelon root (*Citrullus Colocynthis* (*colocynthis*)). The plant has anti-inflammatory, diuretic, and neuroprotective properties. Here below is a method for preparing an alcohol tincture and a discussion of its potential use in complex therapy and rehabilitation after stroke.

The aim of the study was to prepare a tincture from the root of wild watermelon.

Introduction: Wild Watermelon (*Citrullus Colocynthis*) is a plant of the Cucurbitaceae family, known for its medicinal properties. The root of wild watermelon contains a complex of biologically active compounds (cucurbitacins, flavonoids), which have a potential therapeutic effect in the context of the prevention and treatment of the consequences of stroke, including neuroprotective, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory effects [6,7,9].

Materials and methods: graduated cylinder, glass container with a sealed lid (≥ 700 ml), gauze, dark glass bottle, alcohol maceration and extraction.

To prepare the tincture, add 50 g of crushed root to 500 ml of 70% alcohol, let it steep for 14 days in the dark, and then filter. The finished product is stored in a dark glass container.

Results: We obtained 500 ml of tincture from the root of wild watermelon, dark yellow in color.

Conclusions: Wild watermelon root tincture is of scientific interest as a potential treatment for comprehensive rehabilitation after stroke. Preliminary data indicate a positive effect on cognitive function and reduced swelling. However, further in-depth pharmacological and clinical studies are needed before it can be implemented into clinical practice.